

Sensitivity and Uncertainty Effects of Technological Uncertainties in Fusion

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ABSTRACT

We present the ongoing work on assessing the effects of technological uncertainties to the sensitivity and uncertainty of quantities of interest (QOI). In this frame, we focus on contribution neutron fields, to identify the parts of the model phases space, with the highest influence to the QOI, followed by a series of Monte Carlo particle transport calculations, which sample from the most-contributing underlying uncertainties.

In this work we present the application of the above mentioned methodology to the results obtained from the FNG WCLL benchmark experiment, assigning realistic uncertainties to the measured results. This highlighted the need for pre-analysis of future experimental proposals, where tolerance requirements for obtaining trustworthy experimental data are identified. Current activities encompass such a pre-analysis for a concrete shielding benchmark experiment, where the effects of geometrical uncertainties are combined with uncertainties in material composition and moisture content, with future developments taking into account the effects of concrete aggregate distribution.

Keywords: Random sampling, contribution field, tritium breeding, concrete, benchmark

1. INTRODUCTION

Assessment of the effects of technological uncertainties on desired observables, such as tritium breeding and concrete shielding performance is crucial for ensuring safety, efficiency and reliability of nuclear systems. These uncertainties, arising from manufacturing tolerance or material behaviour under different conditions i.e. seasonal moisture changes and water retention in concrete, can significantly impact the predictive performance of a system, leading to either over-conservative and economically inefficient, or under-performing or potentially unsafe designs. In benchmark experiments specifically, it is vital to assess the effects of those uncertainties, as they introduce a level of ambiguity, making it difficult to ascertain whether discrepancies between calculated and experimental results stem from deficiencies in the nuclear data or from the experimental setup itself. If the technological uncertainties in a benchmark experiment are not well characterized and minimized, they can propagate into the adjusted nuclear data, leading to inaccuracies and increased uncertainties. It is therefore paramount to determine these effects and minimize them at the conceptual stages of the benchmark experiment design.

In this paper we present the assessment of the geometrical uncertainty effects on the reaction rate measurements of the Water Cooled Lithium Lead (WCLL) breeding blanket mock-up benchmark experiment performed at the Frascati Neutron Generator (FNG). We utilize the contribution field calculations

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to determine the parts of geometry contributing most to the quantity of interest (QOI), hence being most susceptible to changes. These most sensitive parts were then varied using random sampling within their uncertainties, and results propagated to determine the ultimate QOI uncertainty and it's sensitivity to the underlying perturbation (1).

An ordinary and heavy concrete benchmark experiment is also being investigated. Apart from the geometrical uncertainties of the experimental assembly, we also study the effects of uncertainty in concrete's constituents such as binders, aggregates, plasticizers and the amount of water retention (free, chemically or physically bound) on it's shielding performance.

2. FNG WCLL EXPERIMENT

The Water Cooled Lithium Lead (WCLL) is one of the breeding blanket (BB) concept candidates for future European Demonstration Fusion Power Reactor (DEMO). A neutron transport mock-up experiment, devoted to the validation of tritium breeding ratio (TBR) and shielding capabilities has been manufactured and irradiated with 14 MeV neutrons at the Frascati Neutron Generator (FNG). The benchmark assembly consists of LiPb blocks, with steel structures and a water manifold, which is filled with poly-methyl methacrylate - PMMA surrogate material, as shown in Figure 1. A series of neutron detectors in the form of neutron activation foils are stacked together, forming detector assemblies, which are located within the LiPb blocks. Due to manufacturing and assembly tolerances, the uncertainty in position of detector assemblies is of the order of 1 mm according to the ENEA team performing these experiments. Same uncertainty levels were reported in terms of the angular misalignment along the length of WCLL experiment and the FNG neutron source, as well as the offset between the source and the WCLL experiment.

Figure 1. Left: Schematics of the centre-cut WCLL model, FNG neutron beam source (red circle) and detector assemblies (white circles) arranged in six columns and two rows. Right: schematic of stacked neutron dosimeter foils in bottom and top detector assemblies. LICO denotes Li_2CO_3 with natural and 95 % enrichment in ^6Li .

2.1. Contributon Analysis

In this part of the analysis we performed a qualitative assessment on which parts of the geometry affects the underlying quantity of interest the most by calculating the contributon field (2), which is performed according to Equation 1:

$$C = \phi^\dagger \cdot \phi \quad (1)$$

where ϕ^\dagger and ϕ are adjoint and forward neutron flux respectively. Our original model of the FNG WCLL benchmark was supplied to us in the form of an MCNP (3) input deck.

Since Monte Carlo particle transport methods are ill posed for calculating the adjoint neutron flux, we

made use of the ADVANTG tool (4), which automatically converts the problem geometry and source distribution into an input deck for a DENOVO (5) deterministic neutron transport solver. This is done by model geometry discretization, material homogenization and angular discretization of the source term. A specific geometry discretization mesh was selected, so as to conform to the model geometry, minimizing the material homogenization part. Quadruple range S_N angular quadrature with eight azimuthal and polar angles was used with 27 neutron energy group cross-sections and convergence criterion for within-group iterations set at 1×10^{-6} . By calculating contribution fields for each neutron dosimetry foil of each detector assembly, we identified most important parts of the geometry: close to the neutron source and close to the neutron dosimeter of interest. The reaction rates were calculated using the IRDFF-II (6) neutron dosimetry library. Figure 2 showcases such contribution fields for different reactions. One can note that in case of thermal reactions, the contribution field is more diffuse compared to fast reactions, except for ${}^6\text{Li}$, where a significant portion of neutrons contributing to the ${}^6\text{Li}(n, T)$ reaction are absorbed in the LiPb shielding.

Figure 2. Normalized Contribution fields for top dosimeter assembly, 5th column for different reaction rates, denoted in their respective colormaps, and cross sections of measured reactions (bottom right) from IRDFF-II nuclear data library.

2.2. Geometrical random sampling

Based on the analysis in previous subsection 2.1 and the reported geometrical uncertainty of the detector assemblies of 1 mm we performed the initial analysis, where the detector positions were selected at random from a Gaussian distribution with the mean value at the nominal dosimeter position, and 1σ uncertainty corresponding to the geometrical uncertainty. Two approaches were investigated: varying the position of a single detector assembly individually i.e. "one at a time", and varying the positions of all detectors simultaneously i.e. "all at once". In order to decrease the total computational time, while still achieving desirable statistical uncertainties, both methods were performed using analogue transport and transport with VR for their validity and inter-comparison. In the latter case, the number of calculations increased significantly compared to the "all at once" method. Both analogue transport and transport with using variance reduction methods (VR) were utilized for their inter-comparison and effects of VR, and to check whether the computational time can be decreased. FW-CADIS VR method (7; 8) was used in the frame of the ADVANTG code (4). 512 samples were drawn from their respective probability density functions - in case of one at a time, for each detector assembly. The transport was performed using the ENDF/B VIII.0 nuclear data libraries (9), with IRDFF-II (6) nuclear data libraries used for reaction rate tallying.

The agreement between the "all at once" and "one at a time" approaches is usually quite good, except for ${}^{93}\text{Nb}(n, 2n)$ reaction where high deviations are present, especially with increasing distance from the source, which we postulate occurs due to shadowing from varying previous detectors, blocking the direct source beam.

For the cases of thermal neutron reactions, one can also note multiple probability density function (PDF) peaks present. The results of the above mentioned outliers are shown in Figure 3.

Apart from the uncertainty estimates, the random sampling methodology also allows for the estimation of sensitivity coefficient. In this particular case, this was done by fitting a linear function using the least squares method, dependent on all the variables, giving a sensitivity profile about its nominal position. An illustrative sensitivity estimate for both one-at-a-time and all-at-once, with and without the VR is shown in Figure 4, which highlights the difference between "all at once" approach, which takes into account cross-correlations, which "one at a time" method does not consider. Upon further discussion with the experimental team, we also added the variation of the mock-up's alignment in position and angle with respect to the FNG source. The source's alignment uncertainty in both translation and in terms of rotational distance to the WCLL assembly was again considered at 1 mm. The PDFs obtained in this analysis are much better behaved, and no PDF with multiple peaks are observe. This analysis was performed with transport libraries ENDF/B-VIII.0 (9), FENDL-3.2b (10) and JEFF-3.3 (11), while IRDFF-v1.05 (12) and IRDFF-II (6) libraries were used for reaction rate tallying and their combinations. An example is showcased in Figure 5. Results regarding the FNG WCLL uncertainty and sensitivity are reported in (1) with the data available in (13).

One can note the high uncertainties in reaction rates stemming from such small deviations in the position and/or orientation, affecting the trustworthiness of the obtained experimental results. This highlights the necessity for establishing the maximum allowed technological uncertainty at the experiment's design stages, to obtain high quality experimental data.

(a) ${}^6\text{Li}(n, T)$ reaction rate PDF, showcasing two distinct peaks. (b) ${}^{93}\text{Nb}(n, 2n)$ reaction rate PDF, showing a discrepant results from the two techniques.

Figure 3. PDFs of reaction rates, depending on position of the detector assembly in question. Both techniques were used with VR - one at a time, and all at once were used. Continuous distributions are obtained by summing normally distributed results from Monte Carlo particle transport, while histograms only considered their mean values. Reference calculation - at a nominal position and 1σ statistical uncertainty.

3. CONCRETE BENCHMARK

The aim of this study was to estimate the expected accuracy of shielding benchmark experiments for ordinary and heavy concrete. The samples were prepared at the Warsaw University of Technology in the form of 5 cm thick blocks with the surface area of $50\text{ cm} \times 50\text{ cm}$. Similarly to the WCLL mock-

Figure 4. Linear sensitivity profile for ${}^6\text{Li}(n, T)$ reaction rate with respect to its deviation from nominal position in a detector assembly, located in top row, 3rd column using different sampling and transport techniques. Black arrows denote the sensitivity vectors, and a clear deviation in the sensitivity trend is observed between all-at-once and one-at-a-time techniques. ENDF-B/VIII.0 library for transport, IRDFF-II library for tallying.

(a) ${}^6\text{Li}(n, T)$ reaction rate PDF in a detector assembly at top row, 3rd column, using different transport libraries. (b) ${}^{93}\text{Nb}(n, 2n)$ reaction rate PDF in detector assembly top row, 5th column, using different transport libraries.

Figure 5. PDF of reaction rates, where detector assembly positions, source positions and misalignment between the source and the the WCLL mock-up are varied and different metrics for the assessment of median value and the corresponding uncertainty. Evaluations performed using the all-at-once technique with different transport libraries. Ref.: result at nominal position with 1σ statistical uncertainty.

up, the proposed concrete shielding mock-up is assembled from those blocks, with detector assemblies consisting of several neutron dosimeter foils placed in-between the blocks as shown in Figure 6. The MCNP input deck was provided to us by the ENEA, which operates the FNG. The effects of two separate sources of uncertainty on the reaction rates and total fluxes in their respective detector positions were studied:

- Geometrical uncertainties in terms of positions of detector assemblies, as well as the position and the orientation of the benchmark assembly with respect to the neutron source. Uncertainties similar to the above-mentioned FNG WCLL were adopted.
- Propagation of material uncertainty in terms of relative water content (RWC) and the relative amount of impurities (RIC) compared to nominal values, were both were sampled from a uniform distribution, ranging between 50–150 % and 0–200 % of their nominal values for water and impurity contents respectively.

Due to the concrete's shielding capabilities, we calculated a set of weight windows, utilizing the FW-CADIS method (7; 8) of the ADVANTG code to preferentially stream neutrons contributing to desired quantities such as neutron spectra in each individual detector assembly.

The uncertainties for thermal neutron reactions are most susceptible to both variations in source-orientation and position of the proposed mock-up as well as to material variation, leading to uncertainties ranging from between 0.2 % to over 45 % for the case of geometry variation in both standard and heavy concrete, and between 0.1 % to over 60 % for the variation of material composition, with fast neutron dosimeter reaction rate uncertainties being generally below 40 %. An example of such an evaluation is shown in Figure 7.

Further studies on the concrete mock-up analysis are foreseen. Currently the concrete is modelled as a homogeneous material, and scripts are being prepared to separately model the aggregate and the binder, according to design basis (14), research (15) and established standards (16).

Figure 6. Left: Schematics of the centre-cut concrete mock-up in relation to the FNG neutron source. Right: Geometrical variations of the detector assemblies translation (black) as well as the translation (red) and orientation (orange) variations of relations between the source and the mock-up.

4. COMPUTATIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Even though the random sampling technique applied here is very powerful, it is very computationally intense. Common running times for each of the perturbed simulation runs on our in-house HPC node equipped with 2x Intel® Xeon® Gold 6148 or Intel® Xeon® Gold 6240R and 192 GB of memory is roughly 120 CPUh, hence this is still not yet feasible for routine assessment of uncertainties and sensitivities, which are performed with deterministic codes, which have difficulties capturing non-linear behaviour, as shown in Figure 3a or non-Normal distributions. However, current advancements on porting the Monte Carlo particle transport codes (17; 18) to graphics processors with 1 to 2 orders of magnitude increases in throughput are challenging that.

5. CONCLUSIONS

We present a set of methods for the assessment of the effect of technological uncertainties on the uncertainty and the sensitivity of the desired observable. Presented methods are based on contribution fields, calculated by a deterministic neutron transport solver, establishing the most important parts of the model geometry, and generating a set of Monte Carlo particle transport calculations based on random sampling within the prescribed technological uncertainties, to obtain a statistically significant sample and the resulting distributions and correlations. We've applied these computational techniques to the WCLL mock-up benchmark experiment, and the proposed concrete benchmark experiments to assess the trustworthiness of the obtained/projected experimental results or determine suitable tolerances. Since these experimental data are subsequently used for the generation of nuclear data libraries, such analyses are a crucial step in both the pre-analysis and post-analysis of experimental data. While still

Figure 7. PDFs due to material and dimensional variation and the resulting linear sensitivity fits, and covariance matrices of their parameters. Ref. is the mean value and the associated 1σ statistical uncertainty to nominal conditions, WWG denotes the use of weight windows VR method. Letters on covariance matrices and equations represent linear sensitivity coefficients, i.e. A, B, C are coefficients for detector position in directions x, y, z, direction, D, E are coefficients for source offset in x and z direction, E represents the angular misalignment between the source and the mock-up, and the RWC and RIC represent the relative water content and impurities content, with respect to nominal values.

being prohibitively computationally expensive for routine execution. New methods of porting Monte Carlo particle transport codes to graphics processors and increasing the throughput by orders of magnitude will make the method much more appealing.

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